

Effects of *Se1* gene on basic vegetative growth of rice

M. Niwa, K. Terakado, and N. Takeda, School of Agriculture, Ibaraki University, Ami-machi, Inashiki-gun, Ibaraki, 300-03, Japan

The *Se1* gene, located on the sixth chromosome of rice (*Oryza sativa*), plays an important role in determining the heading time in many rice varieties (Yokoo et al 1980). Through backcrossing, one of the alleles on the *Se1* locus, *Se1-u*, was introgressed from Malaysian rice variety Morak Sepilaito to a genetic background of Fujisaka 5, which has *Se1-e* (Yokoo and Fujimaki 1971). This occurrence suggested that *Se1-u* brought late heading by increasing photoperiod sensitivity. Yokoo and Kikuchi (1982) proposed that *Se1-u* controlled basic vegetative growth.

Our objectives in this study were to clarify the effects of *Se1-e* on vegetative growth and determine whether those effects varied with photoperiod.

Two near-isogenic lines of rice with the genetic background for Fujisaka 5 and different alleles on the *Se1* locus, ER (*Se1-e*) and LR (*Se1-u*), were exposed to various photoperiod regimes in two series of experiments.

In the first series, the plants were seeded and grown in a phytotron at 28°C for 10 d under a 24-h, long-day (LD) photoperiod. Then some of the plants were shifted to a 12-h, short-day (SD) photoperiod at 4-d intervals (LD-SD shifting). In the second series, LD-SD shifting was conducted, using a 10- or 13-h photoperiod as SD and a

24-h photoperiod as LD in the open air chamber with a mean temperature of 32°C.

Three plants were grown per pot; two pots were used per treatment. White fluorescent light (600 lx at the soil surface) was supplemented with sunlight to prolong photoperiod as needed.

1. Days after sowing to heading of isogenic lines ER and LR, as affected by days after sowing when the plants were alternately shifted from 12 to 24 h photoperiod every 4th day.

2. Days from sowing to heading of isogenic lines ER (a) and LR (b) as affected by days from sowing when the plants were shifted from a 10- or 13-h to a 24-h photoperiod.

In the first series, the horizontal parts of the line graphs were determined by averaging days to heading (DTH), which did not differ significantly from those of the control plants grown under 12 h SD from sowing to heading (Fig. 1). Increase in DTH with days from sowing to shifting was approximated by linear regression using significantly larger DTH than those of the control.

Consequently, the turning points of the graphs project estimated days after sowing during which SD did not accelerate DTH. These days are the photoperiod-insensitive phase (PIP) for each isolate. The estimated length of PIP was 24.8 d for ER and 18.0 d for LR.

In the second series, the estimated length of PIP for each isolate and for each photoperiod regime was 16.2 d for ER-10 SD, 18.8 d for ER-13 SD, 12.7 d for LR-10 SD, and 10.7 d for LR-13 SD (Fig.2). Here, ER also exhibited longer PIP than LR. PIP did not differ significantly between regimes within the same isolate.

We concluded that *Se1* affected not only photoperiod sensitivity but also duration of PIP, and that duration of PIP did not vary with photoperiod but rather with temperature.

Cited references

- Yokoo, M, Fujimaki H. 1971. Tight linkage of blast resistance with late maturity observed in different indica varieties of rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 21:35-39.
- Yokoo M, Kukuchi F, Nakane A, Fujumaki H. 1980. Genetical analysis of heading time by aid of close linkage with blast resistance in rice. *Bull. Natl. Inst. Agric. Sci.* D31:96 - 126.
- Yokoo M, Kukuchi F. 1982. Monogenic control of basic vegetative phase and photoperiod-sensitive phase in rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 32: 1-8. ■

Genetic and cytochemical analysis of high 57-kD polypeptide mutants in rice

Y. Takemoto, M. Y. Son, T. Ito, and H. Satoh, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University, Fukuoka 812, Japan; T. Kumamaru, Plant Genetics and Breeding Laboratory, Japan Tobacco Inc., Iwata, Sizuoka 438, Japan; and M. Ogawa, Faculty of Home Economics, Yamaguchi Women's University, Yamaguchi 753, Japan

High 57-kD polypeptide mutants (57H mutants) were induced by mutagen N-

methyl-N-nitrosourea (MNU) treatment (Kumamaru et al 1988), while the 57H spontaneous mutants were found in northern Asian varieties. Four 57H mutant loci (*esp2*, *Glup1*, *glup2*, and *glup3*) have been located on chromosomes 11, 9, 9, and 4, respectively (Satoh et al 1994).

The 57-kD polypeptides of these mutants reacted with anti-glutelin β subunit antibody, indicating that 57H mutants accumulate 57 kD glutelin precursors. Glutelins in wild-type Kinmaze were extracted using 1% lactic acid solution (acid solution). The presence of prolamins did not affect extraction of glutelins at all. In

esp2 mutant CM1787, the glutelin precursors could not be extracted without first removing the prolamins. In *Glup1* mutant EM61 and *glup2* mutant EM305, the glutelin precursors were extracted to a slight extent by acid solution, whereas removing the prolamins promoted extensive extraction of glutelin precursors.

These results indicate that glutelin precursors in these mutants coexist with prolamins. In *glup3* mutant HO1274, the glutelin precursors were extracted as easily as the glutelins of Kinmaze, suggesting that the deposition site of the glutelin precursors is different from that of the prolamins.